

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE HISTORICAL LEGACY OF THE AGHGOYUNLU STATE, WHICH REMAINS TO THIS DAY AND HAS A SPECIAL PLACE IN THE HISTORY OF AZERBAIJANI STATEHOOD

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Abstract

Historically, this article covers the XIV-XV centuries. The state of Aghgoyunlu was created by the Turkish who lived in the east of Anatolia. Since the middle of the XV century, the leadership of the Aghgoyunlu has been in Azerbaijan. Playing a great role in the formation of the Azerbaijani people, the Aghgoyunlu occupy an important place in the history of statehood. The Aghgoyunlu, who ruled most of Anatolia, defeated the Karagoyunlu in the Battle of Mush in 1467 and captured a large area to Baghdad. In 1468, King Hassan laid the foundation of the Aghgoyunlu state. During the reign of the King Hasan, the Aghgoyunlu state became a powerful military-political state in the Near and Middle East. Since its foundation, this state left a lot of cultural heritage in the territories. In this period, science, art, crafts, architecture, etc. developed too. Up to 60 of the most advanced scientists of the East worked in the king's library. Even during the reign of King Hasan, the Holy Kuran was translated into Azerbaijani Turkish. Libraries, mosques, madrassas, baths, palaces, bridges, fortresses, covered bazaars, etc. were built in various cities of Azerbaijan in a very beautiful architectural style. has spread its history till today. The architectural monuments were built with a special plan and adapted to the vegetation. We can show these monuments the buildings in the city of Tabriz. Historical monuments are the main sources confirming the existence of Aghgoyunlu people in Anatolia. Safa Madrasa is one of the most magnificent monuments built in a complex manner in Diyarbakir. Verses from the Koran can be found in the inscriptions of the built religious monuments. The minaret of the mosque is decorated with verses from the Koran. It should be noted that Aghgoyunlu developed calligraphy. These mosques were decorated with special calligraphers' writings. Eight-pointed stars found in Turkish monuments are often found in monuments. These monuments reflect the Turkish-Islamic trace in every style. Among the monuments, tombs and grave monuments carry the history of Aghgoyunlu and their ethnicity and culture to the present day. Tombstones with figures of rams, horses and others prevail among grave monuments. Buda confirms the continuation of the ancient tradition of the Turks during the Aghgoyunlu period.

The historical monuments which were studied here are a very valuable source for studying the history of the Aghgoyunlu people in Anatolia, modern Azerbaijan, Iran (South Azerbaijan), both politically and culturally. By studying the monuments, we also get information about the historical, religious, social, and ethnic groups in the places where the Aghgoyunlu people dominate. This article provides detailed information about all the monuments belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period and explains about their modern condition, style and purpose. The topic we are discussing is very important for the study of the monuments in the areas that dominated by Aghgoyunlu.

Keywords: Aghgoyunlu, Hasan Padshah, monument, mosque, madrasa, tomb, grave.

INTRODUCTION: The Aghqoyunlu state, which holds a significant place in the history of Turkic statehood, has consistently attracted the attention of historians, archaeologists, and researchers. The historian M.Kh. Yinanchin, giving extensive information about the history of the Aghqoyunlu, referred to Gazi Ahmed Gaffari, the author of the works "Jahan ara" and "Nagaristan", and noted that the Aghqoyunlu had settled in Anatolia-Diyarbakir since ancient times. At the same time, Heydar Razi confirmed this idea. The 16th century historian Ibrahim Harir talks about the history of the Aghqoyunlu and its relations with the Seljuks in his work "Tarishi Humayuni". We get the most extensive information about the historical origin of the Aghqoyunlu from Abubakar Tehrani's work "Kitabi - Diyarbakriye". In this work, it is stated that the Aghqoyunlu were a dynasty from the Bayandur tribe of the Oghuz region. For this reason, in some sources, the Aghqoyunlu were called "Bayanduriye" or Bayandur. Z.V. Togan, while analyzing the Oghuz epic, states that the Bayandurs, like other Hun tribes, entered Azerbaijan from the 5th

century through the Caucasus Derbent and lived in the Goycha and Lake Van regions. In general, the Aghgoyunlu, who settled in Eastern Anatolia in Azerbaijan, played an important role in the political, cultural, and ethnic composition of these territories. As Faruk Sumer noted, he considers the modern Turks of Eastern Anatolia to be the successors of the Garagoyunlu (Azerbaijani Turkish state - 1375-1468) and the Aghqoyunlu [T. Najafli. Baku-2012. p189.191]. As we learn about the history of the Aghqoyunlu from works, we also get acquainted with historical monuments that have survived to this day.

The historical and architectural monuments of the Bayandur-Aghgoyun period from the Oghuz tribes are discussed in this article. The Aghgoyunlu state has a special place in the history of Turks and specially in the history Azerbaijan statehood. The Aghgoyunlu state was brought to the state status by Kara Yöyük Osman Bey (1402-1431). Hasan becomes King when he turns the state into the strongest state. In 1453, he became the head of the Aghgoyunlu principality (picture 1). In the beginning, the territory of the Aghgoyunlu state, which

center was Diyarbakir, extended from the east of Mardi to the west of Urfa, from the north to Erzurum and the north of Sivas. Many cultural and architectural monuments, mosques, madrasahs, libraries, etc. were built in the areas dominated by the Aghgoyun people. These monuments are the main sources of the history of the Aghgoyun people. It should be noted that the history of the Aghgoyunlu people, who left a great mark in history, has always attracted the interest of historians, travelers, and geographers. In the article we researched and discussed about the monuments that are the main source for studying the history of the Aghgoyunlu people. It is found in Western Azerbaijan (now Armenia - the historical lands of Azerbaijan) and in Azerbaijan. It is possible to see the traces of Turkish-Islamic culture in all these monuments. The reason why the ram and horse statues on the graves are more predominant (a tradition of the Turks since ancient times) is a sign of Turkish culture.

Both Sunni and Shia mosques built during the Aghgoyunlu period were dominant in Anatolia. Some of these mosques were later restored by the Ottomans, some were destroyed, and some of them have survived to this day. Most of these mosques, built in the 15th century, have survived to this day. The feature that attracts the main attention in the architectural style of these mosques is the central and single tower mosques. The important monuments built during the rule of Aghgoyunlu also confirm that their cultural heritage prevailed in the areas they ruled. We trace the cultural heritage of the Aghgoyunlu state through monuments in all areas a part from Anatolia, especially the city of Tabriz. When we examine the architectural monuments, it becomes clear that these works in the state were under the control of the center, and architects and craftsmen were specially trained. Even in the Ottoman period, in Anatolia, with the laws of Uzun Hasan in force for many years, we can observe the exquisite design of architectural monuments. The observation of the same monument in Nakhchivan and other areas of Azerbaijan is an indicator of a single culture.

Among the surviving monuments from Aghgoyunlu, grave monuments are dominated. These monuments consist of horse and ram statues on graves. In Kars, Iğdir, and Erzurum, ram statues belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period can be found. The most famous grave monuments that have come down to today are the Zeynal Bey mausoleum (monumental tomb) in Hasankeyf and the Amir Bayandur mausoleum that located in Ahlat. Along with grave monuments, this period is also famous for its castles, bridges, and baths. It was even restored in the castles built before the Aghgoyunlu during the reign of King Hasan. One issue should be specially emphasized that the Garagoyunlu architectural style is observed in many monuments. This was not a coincidence. Decorations with examples of Kufi writing in Tabriz architectural monuments can also be observed in the Aghgoyunlu monuments and the patterns were the same in both Karagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu.

The topic that we studied is very important from the point of view of the history of the Aghgoyunlu state, and most importantly in Azetbaycan-Turkish-Islamic

culture. Historical monuments carry the past to the present and keep the traces of the people and the state to which they belong in any form (even if they are destroyed).

For the study of the history of Aghgoyunlu are of great importance both written sources and historical-architectural monuments. The most valuable sources for the study of this period are found in the Topkapı Palace Archives which located in Istanbul. The letters in this archive dominate the study of Ottoman diplomatic relations with Aghgoyunlu. The history of Aghgoyunlu it is present in valuable museum exhibits. These exhibits adorn the museums of the History Museum of Azerbaijan, the Military Museum of Turkey and many countries of the world (picture 2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11). The historical heritage of the Aghgoyunlu period is also found in the Tabriz Azerbaijan Museum in Iran. The city of Tabriz (the capital of the Aghgoyunlu state) located in the northwest of Iran sheds light on the history of Aghgoyunlu with its historical monuments and museum exhibits. The ram and sheep-headed tombstones in the Tabriz Azerbaijan Museum were collected from the northwest of modern Iran in 1957 and are exhibited in the museum. The ten tombstones collected are attributed to the Garagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu periods. Epigraphic inscriptions, drawings, seals, daggers, arrows and other signs are found on the tombstones, except for two. The seals here indicate the lineage of the tomb owner. In general, the double-headed tombstones belonging to the Garagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu periods of Azerbaijan in Tabriz are an indicator of the pre-Islamic culture of the Turks not only in Tabriz, but also in other historical lands of Azerbaijan, and in Anatolia in general [A.Ersay. Ankara-2023.p.850-857]. Even the toteism of the Turks is found in literary works as well as in monuments. We can trace examples of this culture in many areas of Azerbaijan, especially in the Gazakh region, until the end of the 19th century. We can also see exhibits belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period in the New York Metropolitan Museum. Helmets belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period are exhibited in the museum.

The scientific novelty of topic: The material and culture samples that existed in the territory of the Aghgoyunlu state (monuments of the Aghgoyunlu period in the territories of modern Azerbaijan, Turkey, Iran) in the XIV-XV centuries have been comprehensively explained for the first time.

Research methods: The basis of the research is the chronological analysis and material culture of the historical-archaeological-architectural monuments of the reign of Aghgoyunlu (1378-1503). Similar and different features were analyzed by the historical methods. Historical-comparative, descriptive, classification and scientific-historical generalization methods were used in the study of the topic.

MAIN TEXT - The founders of Aghgoyunlu state were Turks who lived in western Anatolia in the 15th-15th centuries. We have watched Aghgoyunlu architecture, cultural monuments, and historical works in all areas dominated by Aghgoyunlu. The Aghgoyunlu people belonged to the Bayandur boys (clan) of the Oghuz Turks and lived west of the Karagoyunlu people who

settled in the east of Asia Minor [Azerbaijan history .2007. p.95]. Firstly, the territory of the Aghgoyunlu state, whose center was Diyarbakir, extended from the east of Mardin to the west of Urfa, from the north to the north of Erzurum and Sivas. In the north, from Bayburt, in the areas where the Tigris River splits into different branches, they lived a winter and steppe lifestyle. In 1467, King Hasan [Uzun Hasan-1453-1478 years] defeated the ruler of Garagoyunlu and united the territories of that state to his own state. The capital was moved from Diyarbakir to the city of Tabriz. In 1469, the territories of Iraq and Iran were included in the composition of the Aghgoyunlu state. For twelve years after 1461, Hasan expanded the territory of the Sultanate and laid the foundations of the Big Aghgoyunlu empire in the territories of Iraq, Azerbaijan, and Iran [H.I. Long market. Ottoman history. 2019. p. 95]. King Hasan, who built such a great state, went down in history not only as a ruler, but also as a person who left a cultural heritage for the future. Many cultural and architectural monuments, mosques, madrasahs, libraries, etc. were built in the areas dominated by the Aghgoyun people. These monuments preserve the heritage and history of the Aghgoyun people. are the main sources of transport. A number of sources even stated that King Hasan built a large palace complex in Tabriz. According to the sources, there were 20,000 rooms in the palace [History of Azerbaijan . 2007. p. 175].

The state of Aghgoyunlu has left a great treasure since its existence. Here we can show the laws of King Hasan (with some changes) implemented until the 1540s. These laws prepared by King Hasan had a great importance in the history of Islamic law, and the country was properly governed thanks to the laws [F.Sümer. 1989. P.274]. During the reign of Aghgoyunlu the other treasures have come down to our days are historical works written. It should be noted that the history of Aghgoyunlu people, who left a great mark in history, has always attracted the interest of historians, travelers, and geographers. Hasan Padshah always gave special importance to scientists, historians and writers in his palace. The most important source for studying the history of the state is Abu Bakr Tirhani's Kitab-i-Diyarbakiriyya. At the same time, we can show the works of Ali Kuschu, Mahmud Sorihi, Mehmet from Shiraz, Abdulhey from Nishapur, Fazlullah and other historians and writers. The famous mathematician Mahmud Can, scientist Isa Savci Masuhiddin, who received special attention during the Aghgoyunlu period, Idris Bitlisi (writer), who later worked in the Ottoman palaces, grew up in the palace of Hasan King [H. Kalesh.2021. p.2]. The Venetian letters (alliance against the Ottomans) are also of special importance for studying the foreign policy of Aghgoyunlu. Historian Ibrahim Harir, who lived in the 18th century, provides information about the places where the Aghgoyunlu tribes lived in his work "History of Humayuni". Historical and archaeological monuments confirm the views of the historian who gave extensive information about the first rule of the Aghgoyunlu in Andarbakir and other areas. The information of Gazi Ahmed Ghaffari and Heydar Razin about the settlement of the Aghgoyunlu in Diyarbakir. the monuments found also confirm.

The article is mainly dealing about the monuments, which are the main source for studying the history of the territories dominated by Aghgoyunlu. Monuments belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period can also be found in Eastern Anatolia, Tabriz (Southern Azerbaijan), Western Azerbaijan (now Armenia - historical Azerbaijan lands) and Modern Azerbaijan. Traces of Turkish-Islamic culture can be seen in all of these monuments. Ram and horse statues on graves. and the reason why it prevails more (a tradition of the Turks since ancient times) is the sign of Turkish culture. Written tombstones belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period also convey a lot of information from a historical point of view. For example, we can show the tombstones in Isfahan from the year 1497 (Hijri-815). The inscriptions on the graves are written in Arabic. The tombstones of the same shape can be found in Mardin, Hasankeyf, Erzincan. It is also found in Erzurum, Kığı and other areas. Zoomof tombstones belonging to Aghgoyunlu period can also be found in the Juga necropolis. The necropolis spans the 13th-15th centuries and is located in the territory of Gulistan village of Julfa district. There are many ram and horse-shaped tombstones belonging to the Karagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu periods in the cemetery. Gravestones of the same shape can be found in many parts of Turkey, Azerbaijan, Western Azerbaijan (now Armenia) (places where the Aghgoyunlu people ruled), from Azerbaijan to Eastern Anatolia. These tombstones swords, various drawings, shields, daggers, etc. are found on it. These drawings are not only decorative, but also provide information about the identity and gender of the person in the grave [R. Bagırlı.Konya-2008.p30]. M. Kh. According to Yinanc's opinion, the Aghgoyun people have been attached to the sheep totem since ancient times and remained loyal to this totem even after accepting Islam.

Both Sunni and Shia mosques that built during the Aghgoyunlu period were dominant in Anatolia. Some of these mosques were later restored during the Ottoman Empire, some were destroyed, and some have survived to this day. We can point to the architectural monuments built during the Aghgoyunlu period and which have survived to this day - the Gutlug Bey mosque and the ceremonial and dervish house. This monument was built in 1389 in the Sinur village of Baybut by Fakhred-din Gutluq Bey, the father of Bayandur. The monument was renovated in 1550 and 1676 and a minaret was erected on it. Today, a part of this monument is in ruins [J.E.Woods.Istanbul-1993.p.391]. At the same time, among the mosques built during the reign of Aghgoyunlu in Anatolia, there are Jahangir mosque built by Pir Ali Bey in Bingöl, Jahangir Bey in Mardin, Hassan and Sara Khatun mosques built by Sultan Hasan in Urfa, Gulabi Bey in Erzincan, Ibrahim Bey in Mardin, Kazim Padshah in Diyarbakir. his name should be specially mentioned. Mosques were not built only by Hasan Padshah and his family members. Among the mosques that were built, there were also mosques that were built by the generals of King Hasan and the governors appointed to the cities. Most of the mosques were built in madrasahs in their courtyards. The most famous madrasahs belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period are Sultan Kazim, Shahsultan, and Golbaşı madrasahs in Urfa, which were built at the end of the 15th century.

We observe the most Aġqoyunlu architecture and historical monuments in the areas of Mardin and Diyarbakir. During our research, we see differences in the style and luxury of Diyarbakir monuments. The fact that Diyarbakir was the capital of the Aġqoyunlu is also confirmed by the historical and architectural monuments built magnificently in the city. Many of these monuments have survived to this day and have carried historical realities to the modern era. When we examine the Aġqoyunlu period monuments of Diyarbakir, we come across two types of architectural monuments. The first type of monuments belongs to the madrasah, mosque, and tomb belonging to the members of the order, which were built in a complex manner. These buildings were also built in a complex manner close to each other. The second type of architectural monuments are monuments consisting of a single small or single building. This mainly includes a single mosque, a tekke (a Sufi house), and so on. These monuments were usually built on the outskirts of the city, outside the center, and very few decorations and works are found in these types of monuments. The more magnificent buildings were built in Diyarbakir, the capital of the Aġqoyunlu dynasty in Anatolia. At the same time, very few of the second type of monuments have survived to this day. The monuments built in a complex (complex) form have survived to this day in better shape [C. Parla. Diyarbakir before the Ottomans. Diyarbakir 2004.p.283]. Among the monuments that have survived to this day and are distinguished by their architectural style, we can mention the Hoca Ahmed Mosque (1489), the Sheikh Mutahhar Mosque (1500), the Sheikh Safi Mosque (15th century). Most of the mosques built during the Aġqoyunlu dynasty (in Urfa, Diyarbakir, Mardin, Erzincan, Elazığ, Bingöl, etc.) have a madrasah section. Another monument built during the Aġqoyunlu period in Diyarbakir is the Safi or Iparli Mosque and Madrasah. The monument is located in the northwest of Diyarbakir. Although no date has been found on the monument, research indicates that it was built during the Aġqoyunlu period. The monument was built by Uzun Hasan (mid-15th century) at the request of Sheikh Cüneyt, the son of Sheikh Ibrahim Safi, grandfather of Shah Ismail [A.K. Kırcaalı. Samsun-2017.s12]. For this reason, it was named the Safi Mosque after the Sheikh. Although the monument is not as large as the mosques belonging to the Aġqoyunlu period in Diyarbakir, it stands out with its special style, interior decoration, and stonework. The minaret of the mosque is decorated with verses from the Quran. Among the Aġqoyunlu mosques that have survived to this day in Diyarbakir, the Nabi Mosque and Lala Bey Mosque also stand out with their architectural style. The monument, built in the 15th century in the Dağ Kapısı area of Diyarbakir, has hadiths of the Prophet written on some of its walls. The mosque, whose minaret collapsed, was restored by the General Directorate of Foundations of the Republic of Turkey in 1960. Lala Bey Mosque was built in the center of Diyarbakir by Lala Kazım Bey. Lala Bey ruled Diyarbakir until Diyarbakir was occupied by the Safavids in 1508. It is said that the monument was built in the late 15th century. The Nabi Mosque, a work of the Aġqoyunlu dynasty, has not survived to this day in its complete state. During

the First World War, Diyarbakir was also under military rule and the Nabi Mosque became a military headquarters. About this state of the monument, Turkish scholar and writer Ali Emiri Efendi notes, "Soldiers were stationed in the mosque decorated with Chinese tiles, Many valuable tiles were torn off and destroyed, Even nothing was left of the mosque decorated with ancient carpets, The carpets there were not seen later" [Yusuf/K/H/Diyarbakir camileri.-2014.p.34]. Part of the monument - the Hanoifi section - began to collapse in 1927. In 1955, the road of the western part of Gazi Street was widened and demolished by the municipality along with the minaret. According to information, the Nabi Mosque, which was built in a complex on a very large area, consisted of the Shafi'i, Hanifi and madrasah sections. We follow the traces of the Aġqoyunlu, which was a Turkish state in every form, from the monuments that were destroyed both as a result of natural disasters and for various reasons, which have survived to this day. Another mosque built during the Aġqoyunlu period in Diyarbakir is the Hoca Ahmed Mosque.

The mosque was built in 1489 by the philanthropist Haji Ahmed. The minaret of the mosque is octagonal. Another mosque built in Diyarbakir in 1500 is the Sheikh Matar Mosque. The monument was built by the Aġqoyunlu Sultan Qasim Bey. The mosque was named after him because it is located near the grave of Sheikh Matar. We can also mention the Four-Legged Minaret monument found in Diyarbakir and which has preserved its grandeur to this day. This minaret, built by Sultan Qasim (1496-1501 - Diyarbakir-Mardin) in 1500, is also called the Sheikh Mutahhar Mosque. The monument was built with white and black stones on four columns. This architectural monument is a rare building of Turkish architecture in Anatolia. The Safi Mosque, whose name we mentioned above, was also built in the same style, that is, on eight columns. This style is considered to be the forerunner of the plan applied by Mimar Sinan in Ottoman architecture. In the name of the Hamza Bey Mosque, built in Diyarbakir by Hamza Bey (1434-1444) in the Inner Castle area, we can note that the monument was destroyed during the First World War and does not exist today. In the Aġqoyunlu monuments located in Diyarbakir, we also see the religious meetings and the content of the ceremonies of this period. In general, the mihrabs, which are the main part of the mosques found in Mardin, Diyarbakir and other areas (even in monuments belonging to the Ottoman period), were a style dating back to the 15th century Aġqoyunlu period. This was a synthesis of the style belonging to the Seljuk, Artuk, and Ayyubid periods in Anatolia before the Aġqoyunlu. We see the strongest form of this style in the Safa Mosque in Diyarbakir [Yusuf K.H.Diyarbakir Camileri-2014.p.20-24]. The interior decoration of mosques and minarets with their exquisite calligraphy (Kufic writing, exquisite calligraphy of verses from the Quran, geometric compositions, nature paintings, etc.) was especially developed during the Aġqoyunlu period. The most important example that all these monuments carry to this day is a strong representation of the Turkic-Islamic culture. At the same time, ram-sheep-headed tombstones from the Garaqoyunlu (1365-1469) and Aġqoyunlu

(1403-1508) periods are found in Diyarbakir [M.Aksoy. 2019.p.104].

One of the magnificent monuments built during the Ag Qoyunlu period is Hasan Castle. The castle was built after the territory in the Persian territory was captured by Uzun Hasan. Such castles were also built in the territories of Nakhchivan, Koyulhisar, Erzurum, and Selmas. Uzun Hasan, who built the castle, also built castles from the time of Uzun Hasan and previous periods, and even the Harput Castle. This tradition, which is a historical heritage, was left to Uzun Hasan by his grandfather, Gara Yöyük Osman Bey. Gara Yöyük Bey had the Ergani Castle repaired in 1402-1403 and donated the key to the castle to the settlement. Some sources have other ideas about the construction of Hasan Castle, stating that it was not built by Hasan Padşah. However, in the Urfa Chronicle of 192, it is stated that the castle and Hasan Padşah Mosque were built during the Ag Qoyunlu period. Evliya Çelebid states that these monuments were built by Uzun Hasan and that they were not named after Hasan Padşah by chance. The monuments built by the Ağqoyunlu, who controlled these territories in 1404-1514, have survived to this day. The date of Hijri 965-AD 1460 on the inscription of Hasan Castle indicates that the monument was built on this date [Cihat A.K. Şanlıurfa camileri. Ankara 1993.p.34-35.; Cihat A.K. Şanlıurfada canlanan tarih. Şanlıurfa Valiliği.1990-1995.].

Most of the mosques built in Erzincan and surrounding areas were built at the end of the 15th century. The monuments that were affected by time and nature were later destroyed by earthquakes. Most of these mosques, built in the 15th century, have survived to this day. The main feature of the architectural style of these mosques is the central and single-towered mosques. Most of the mosques built during the Aghgoyunlu era (in Urfa, Diyarbakir, Mardin, Erzincan, Elazığ, Bingöl, etc.) have a madrasa section. Tombs and zaviya houses built in memory of Aghgoyunlu princes, ancient baths, most of the castles were destroyed mainly in earthquakes in the region.

The tombs built on graves during the Aghgoyunlu period are very magnificent from the point of view of architecture. These tombs were built on the graves of the family members of the Aghgoyunlu ruling class. Here are the tombs of Ugurlu Mehmet in Erzincan, Hamza's tomb in Mardin, Zeynel Bey's tomb built on the left bank of the Tigris River, Halil Bey's tomb in Mush, Korkmaz's in Bayburt. We can mention the tomb of Bey. The most beautiful of these tombs (in terms of architecture) is the tomb of Zeynal Bey. This tombstone was the most beautiful of the Aghgoyunlu tomb monuments (picture 20). The tomb was built by Hasan Padshah in 1474 for his son Zeynel, who died in the battle of Otlugbel. , there were baths and other buildings [J.E. Woods, Istanbul -1993, p. 394] . There are also three important tombs from the Aghqoyunlu period in the Mardin region. These tombs belong to Hamza Bey, son of Gara Yoluk Osman Bey, his grandson Jahangir Bey, and his son Jahangir Bey's son Gasin Bey. There is the tomb of Gutlug Bey in Bayburt, the tomb of Bayandur Bey in Ahlat, and tombs from the Aghqoyunlu period can also be found in Erzincan and Diyarbakir.

Most of the monuments-mosques belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period were built in the form of a complex [H.Gundogdu. 2015.p.567]. In all complex monuments, mosques, madrasahs, libraries and other buildings were united. The important monuments built during the rule of Aghgoyunlu also confirm that their cultural heritage prevailed in the areas they ruled. Apart from Anatolia, we trace the cultural heritage of the Aghgoyunlu state through monuments in all areas, especially the city of Tabriz. When examining the architectural monuments, it becomes clear that in the state these works were under the control of the center, and architects and masters were specially trained. In all traces, we follow the style of the Seljuks, Turkish-Islamic culture. Even in the Ottoman period, in Anatolia, with the laws of Uzun Hasan in force for many years, we can observe the exquisite design of architectural monuments. The observation of the same monument in Nakhchivan and other areas of Azerbaijan is an indicator of a single culture.

Among the historical-architectural monuments, we can mention the mansions built during the Aghgoyunlu period. The area of the mansions was large and consisted of many rooms, warehouses, kitchens, stoves and additional buildings. Even special people were appointed to carry out the internal works of the mansion. Because the mansions were very big. Among these mansions, we can point out the Ferahshah mansion in Bayburt and the Jahangir mansion built by Jahangir Bey, the brother of Hasan Padshah in Mardin. We get information about the Jahangir mosque from written sources. Because the monument has not survived. According to the information, in 1474, a traveler named Barbaro, who had to go from Cyprus to Tabriz and passed through Mardin, stayed in a guest house near the palace. Kalesh. 2021. p. 10].

We can show the bridges to another architectural monument built during the Aghgoyunlu period. These bridges were built in the 15th century. We can show the Bayandur and Hasan bridges as the most famous bridges according to their architectural style. The Bayandur bridge is a one-eyed bridge built in Ahlat. It shows that it was built during the Bey period. It is said that the bridge was built in the middle of the XV century. The bridge has survived to this day, even with ruined form. Hasan Bridge was built in the north of Erzurum. The bridge was a stone bridge and was built by Hasan King. This bridge was mostly used during military marches. This bridge facilitated the marches of the Aghgoyun people against the Georgians [Hinz W. Ankara 1992.p.97].

Among the surviving monuments from Aghgoyunlu, grave monuments dominate. These monuments consist of horse and ram statues on graves (picture 21,22,23,24,25) . These grave monuments are more common in Nakhshivan and Zangezur in many parts of Azerbaijan. In Kars, Igdir, and Erzurum, ram statues belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period can be found. The most famous grave monuments that have come down to today are the Zeynal Bey mausoleum (monumental tomb) in Hasankeyf and the Amir Bayandur mausoleum located in Ahlat. Along with grave monuments, this period is also famous for its castles,

bridges, and baths. Even during the reign of Uzun Hasan, it was restored in the castles that were built before the Aghgoyunlu. One issue should be specially emphasized that many monuments follow the Garagoyunlu architectural style. This was not a coincidence. Decorations with examples of Kufic writing in the architectural monuments of Tabriz are also observed in the Aghgoyunlu monuments. The patterns were the same in both Karagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu, there is no significant difference in the architectural styles of the monuments belonging to both states. Few monuments from the Garagoyunlu period have survived in separate areas, i.e. in Van, while monuments from the Aghgoyunlu period have survived in Diyarbakir, Erzincan, and Mardin [B.Doğan, A.Doğanay-2017.p.653]. Tombstones with figures of sheep belonging to the Garagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu periods show that they were a Turkmen-Turkic state and that their traditions were also preserved in the monuments [H. Keleş.2021. p.3]. Today, very few of the monuments mentioned above remain. Most of the mosques, palaces and other buildings, most of which were complex buildings (a characteristic feature of Aghgoyunlu period architecture), remained. The mosque in Erzincan was completely destroyed in the earthquake of 1939. The remains of the mosque in Mardin remain. but the mosque remains [J.E. Woods.1993. p.392].

One of the most magnificent monuments built in Mardin during the Ag Qoyunlu period is the Qasimiyya (Sultan Qasin) Madrasah. The monument was built on a large area in the north of the Mesopotamian plain. The monument covers a 30-meter-long platform and is 20 meters high. The Qasimiyya Madrasah was built after it was taken over by the Ag Qoyunlu ruler Uzun Hasan in Mardin (after the Qara Qoyunlu dynasty) and given to the management of his brother Jahangir Mirza. It is said that Jahangir Mirza's son Sultan Qasim brought many craftsmen and architects from Azerbaijan and Tabriz and had it built. Qasim Sultan, who tried to eliminate the consequences of Timur's (1336-1405) invasions, resumed the construction of Mardin. It is said that the first buildings of the monument, built in the southwest of the city, were attributed to the Artuklu period. Historian-archaeologist Alberd Gabriel states that the other buildings of the Qasimiyya Madrasah were built after the Zinciriyya Madrasah [Nilgün F.Mardin 2024.p.72]. In addition to the Zinciriyya Madrasah, many buildings (madrasah, mosque, hahah, spring, etc.) were built by Aghgoyunlu Qasim Sultan. For this reason, it is called the Qasimiyya Madrasah. This madrasah, which was the great work of Qasim Sultan, was the educational and scientific center of Anatolia in general. In addition to religious knowledge, secular sciences were taught in the madrasah. The madrasah was the first center where education continued until the First World War (1914-1918) [Hicran H.H, Hashim.A. Jilses-2018. p. 13]. The madrasa, which was used as a military barracks during the war, has been operating as a museum belonging to the Mardin Governorate since the 1960s and has been open for worship as a mosque since 2007. The madrasa, which was built in 1469, is one of the largest historical buildings in Mardin. The two-story madrasa also consists of a mosque section. The zawiya (dervish meeting houses) and tombs found

around it indicate that the building is a complex building. The monument, which carries many historical information from the 15th century to the present, also attracts attention with its architectural secrets. The monument was built in such a way that the light is distributed evenly from sunrise to sunset. It is possible to use natural light with the sun's rays very skillfully. The reason for this kind of construction was to illuminate all the rooms in the science center. Even the doors of the classrooms were very low so that students could bow their heads as a sign of respect when approaching their teachers. This also meant that science was given great value during the Aghqoyunlu period. From this perspective, as we study the monument, we not only learn historical knowledge from the past to the present, but also the material and spiritual values left by the Aghqoyunlu, a Turkish state. These monuments preserve the traces of the Aghqoyunlu since the time of Gara Yoluk Osman Bey, when they conquered Mardin and the northern regions of Erzincan. In Erzincan, Harput, Mardin and many areas on the banks of the Tigris and Euphrates, which were completely captured until 1430, the Agqoyunlu's own line was felt in the monuments. In all the Anatolian territories captured by the Agqoyunlu, especially the capital Diyarbakir-Amid city and Mardin, many mosques, madrasas, baths, castles, and tombs were built during the reign of Hasan Sultan. This restoration and construction work were also carried out in Harput and the surrounding areas, which were under the rule of the Agqoyunlu for 40 years. Hasan Sultan, who had mints in Harput, also restored the Harput Castle. Because Harput was one of the main important centers of the Aghqoyunlu. The Italian traveler Barbaro stated this in his writings and noted, "He said that the Harput Castle is very magnificent and here Despina Khatun, the wife of Sultan Hasan (daughter of the Trabzon emperor), lives in Harput" [Zekiye.T.Elazığ-2013.s575; Walter H.Ankara 1992.s54.]. One of the monuments built in Harput during the Aghqoyunlu period is the Saray Khatun Mosque, which was built by Sara Khatun, the mother of Uzun Hasan, who is said to have ruled Harput. The monument, which consisted of only a mosque part and was built in the city's Bugday Square, was later rebuilt in a very large form. In the area near the building, which was built as a complex-complex, typical of Agqoyunlu architecture, there was also a madrasah, a small school, a fountain, and the Cimshit Bath, which remains to this day. The monument was renovated in 1598 by Mustafa oğlu during the reign of Murad III (1574-1595) and restored again in 1843. The first construction of the monument was built during the reign of Sara Khatun and was covered with wood [Hanza G. C-8.Ankara-2002.p259]. Sara Khatun Mosque is among the most visited works of the region by tourists today.

We also follow Agqoyunlu works in Hakkari. Hakkari was under the rule of the Aghqoyunlu dynasty in the second half of the 15th century. One of the most beautiful works of the Aghqoyunlu dynasty in Hakkari is the Müydan Madrasah. The Madrasah was built in 1472. The monument is currently located in the Meydan neighborhood of Hakkari. The monument was restored by the General Directorate of Foundations of Turkey [Hamza.K.2006.p72].

The period of Aghgoyunli rule is the period of further development of the unique Azerbaijani architecture. According to X.Gasimov, this period is the age of classical maturity. This period is characterized by the stability and exhaustion of Azerbaijani architecture [T.Najafli. Baku-2012. p.465]. Progress in the construction of more religious buildings can be seen both in the period of Karagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu. After the inheritance of Garagoyunlu passed into the hands of Aghgoyunlu, the center

of Aghgoyunlu was moved from Diyarbakir to Tabriz. Hasan Padshah (Hijri-871-883, AD-1466-1478 years) built a magnificent library in Tabriz. Tabriz was at the forefront with magnificent architectural buildings even during the reign of Hasan the King. However, only a small part of the architectural monuments created during this period have survived. The Aghgoyunlu-Turkmen palace style was preserved in the architecture of Shiraz and Tabriz during the reign of King Hasan and his sons Sultan Khalil (1478) and Sultan Yaqub (1478-1490) A.Okay. Ankara. p. 350].

Although there are many memorial buildings and tombs, there was more development in religious buildings. R. Klavikhon, who was in Tabriz, told about his observations that "in this city there are very large mosques and buildings decorated with amazing carvings and networks, decorated with beautiful glass" [History of Azerbaijan resources on Baku-1989. p.320]. The fact that the city of Tabriz was the capital gave further impetus to its development. The buildings were adapted to the greenery and vegetation under the supervision of Hasan the King himself. There were large gardens in the city of Tabriz. The Garden of Nasriyya, one of the rarest and largest buildings of this period, was built by Hasan the King. One of the rarest pearls of urban planning culture was the North Garden built by Sultan Yaqub (1478-1490). The largest of the covered bazaars built in Tabriz during the reign of King Hasan was the Caesarea bazaar. This bazaar was famous as the most famous bazaar in the eastern countries. covered with an arch. X. Inalcik stated that the city of Tabriz was the most important trade center both before and during the Aghgoyunlu dynasty. Most Italian merchants came to Tabriz. Ambrosi Kontarini, who was the ambassador at that time, also provides extensive information about the trade of Tabriz. It states that there are large houses and shops similar to alcazeria in the city. And alcazar was the name of the castles or castles built in the Moorish style in Spain. Iosafat Barbaron states in his travelogue that there were multi-room caravanserais for merchants in Isfahan and Tabriz.

Tabriz Friday Mosque is one of the most beautiful architectural monuments in Tabriz. This magnificent architectural monument was built by Hasan Padshah. More information about it is provided by the travel expert Evliya Çelebi. According to information, after the death of Hasan the King, he was buried in the courtyard of this mosque. The mosque was decorated with patterns and eyebrows on all sides. The mosque was a work of art. The southern door of the building was decorated with inscriptions written in beautiful lines, carved patterns, grids, and patterns in the Greek style. Inscriptions on all the doors and windows. [T. Najafli.Baku-2012. p.469]. All these inscriptions were

written in the script of Yakut Mustasim. There were two beautiful pieces of stone on both sides of the altar. [Chalabi. Baku-1997. p. 92]. During this period, the art of Islamic miniatures and calligraphy developed in Aghgoyunlu palaces. According to S.Arshari, the taliq line developed by Khaja Taj Salmani was brought to a level of art by Khaja Abulhay in Aghgoyunlu palace. This art was used in the decoration of Aghgoyunlu palaces. We can mention the brothers Abdulrahim and Abdulkarim among these art masters. Abdulrahim Sultan Khalil worked in the palace of Aghgoyunlu Yaqub when he was the governor of Shiraz.

Another architectural monument built during the Aghgoyunlu period was the palace complex built in the Sahibabad square of Tabriz. This palace was separated from the center of Tabriz by a valley. The difference of the palace was that this palace was built in a garden, a forest. The palace was called "Hashtbehisht" (Eight Heavens). the palace consisted of four large halls and many rooms. The construction of the palace began in 1478. It was completed during the reign of Sultan Yaqub. According to the information given by Fazlullah ibn Ruzbihan Khunji, this turquoise palace in the center of the Sahibabad garden was built and completed in 1486. The palace had pointed towers [Khundzhi F. Translation - T.A. Minorskoy. Baku-1987. C. 1987]. The most important information about the Hashtbehisht palace complex is provided by a Venetian merchant who traveled to Tabriz in 1506 in his travelogue. The merchant states that the palace was started to be built by Hasan Padshah [R. Bayramov. Baku. 2013. p. 26]. The Venetian merchant also states that the palace is located near the city and there is a Friday mosque surrounded by walls [T. Najafli.Baku-2012. p.470]. This mosque was very big and consisted of many rooms. The mosque was decorated with golden water. All the doors in the palace were decorated with gold and blue (picture 19) . The corridor had marble columns. At the same time, a healing house was built near the palace. During the reign of King Hasan and Sultan Yaqub, it is reported that more than a thousand patients were treated here [T. Gündüz.İstanbul. 2007.s161-164; S. Ershahin. Ankara-2002. p. 228-229].

Although the monuments belonging to the Aghgoyunlu have not survived in their original state compared to the grave monuments, they are of great importance from a historical point of view. Because most of the Aghgoyunlu monuments were built as a complex. For this reason, only one of the architectural monuments built in the form of a complex has remained. Even in the monuments of Diyarbakir, mosques, madrasahs, meeting houses, tombs belonging to two different peoples belonged to one complex building. During the reign of Uzun Hasan, special attention was paid to the minaret and style of mosques. In Mardin, the ornate urban architecture belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period is most noticeable. However, the battle of Otlugbel in 1473 caused Aghgoyunlu to decline in architecture as well as in the political arena.

CONCLUSION: Based on the monuments we investigated, it is known that the monuments belonging to the Aghgoyunlu period have their own characteristics, both in terms of architecture and grave monuments. In the monuments of this period, we see that the

buildings are in the form of a complex. The minarets of the built mosques were decorated with patterns, and memorial tombs were predominant.

Aghgoyunlu states were also a cultural center in terms of geography. Following the traces of both Azerbaijani (Garagoyunlu, Aghgoyunlu, Safavi-North, South Azerbaijan) and Ottoman culture in the monuments, we see that these monuments play the role of a bridge in terms of culture.

We follow Aghgoyunlu monuments more in Diyarbakir, Mardin, Bingöl, Erzincan, Urfa, Tabriz. In the monuments, we can also see the religious meetings and the contents of the ceremonies of this period. In this period, the main buildings were square and rectangular, and the top of the buildings in the center was semi-spherical (dome). Complex buildings were built mainly in the city center. Crown-shaped entrance doors are found in mosques and many other buildings. Marble stones were used in buildings. Mosques were built very ornately from the inside. Six-, twelve-, and eight-pointed stars, vegetable patterns, and symbolic motifs are found in the decorations. Tombstones with the figures of rams and horses found in the ancient Turks are found in grave monuments.

Today, Aghgoyunlu monuments are located outside the current borders of Azerbaijan, especially the city of Tabriz. In all the monuments (in the Turt-Oghuz homeland with Aghgoyunlu territories) we see traces of Turkish-Islamic culture and these states. Today in Anatolia, Western Azerbaijan (modern Armenia), Tabriz - the city of Southern Azerbaijan (modern Iran) and other areas, we see the remains of Aghgoyunlu heritage. The topic we are researching is very important from the point of view of studying the history of the Aghgoyunlu state, and most importantly Azatbayjan-Turkish-Islamic culture. In the architectural style of the monuments, the Turkish culture, which had its roots in Central Asia in the 14th-15th centuries and was dominant in Anatolia and Azerbaijan (All Azerbaijan), played the role of a bridge, transferring it from earlier centuries to the Ottoman and Safavid periods. It is impossible to give information about the monuments of this state in just one article. The study of these monuments is an urgent issue and should always be in the center of attention. Historical monuments carry the past to the present day and in every form (even if they are destroyed) keep the traces of the people and the state to which they belong (Asadova A.V.).

References:

- Doğan, B., Doğanay, A. (2017). An assessment of architectural and artistic style in the Akkoyunlu and Karakoyunlu states. *Human and social sciences research journal*. volume-6. issue-1.. pp. 652-682
- Gundogdu, H. (2015). Aghgoyunlu period architecture. *New Turkey* -72, p. 567
- Uzuncharşılı, I.H. (2019). Ottoman history. II-vol. *Turkish Tarih Kurumu*. 12 editions. Ankara. p. 755
- History of Azerbaijan. (2007), 7 - in the volume. III - vol. (XIII-XVIII centuries). Baku. Elm. pp. 592+56 p. Illustration
- Kelesh, H. (2021). Akkoyunlu cultural heritage in Anatolia: historical artifacts. Gazi University, Gazi Faculty of Education. Secondary education social fields education department. Department of History Education.. 2006 .c 38. pp. 63-80
- Woods, J.E. (1993). 300-year Turkish empire Akkoyunlular. Ek Yazılar. prof dr. M. Sozun, N. Sakaoglu. National publications . p. 424
- Sumer, F. (1989). Akkoyunlular. TDV. IA. volume-II. Istanbul. p. 274
- Hinz, V. (1992). Uzun Hasan and Sheikh Junayd, translated by T. Bayıklıoğlu. Ankara. p. 99
- Najafli, T.H. (2012). Karagoyunlu and Aghgoyunlu states of Azerbaijan (in modern Turkish historiography). Baku-Chaşıoğlu. p.604
- Sources on the history of Azerbaijan. (1989). Baku, Azerbaijan University Press-. p. 328
- Çalabi, E. (1997). Travelogue. Written in Turkish and author of comments S. Onullahi. Baku-ADN-. p. 97
- Khundzhi, F.R. Tarikh-i alam-arai-amini. Translation from English to Russian. T.A. Sultans and Wars through the Eyes of Travelers. (2007). Giovanni Maria Angioiello-Venice merchant and Vincenzo Alexandrini's travelogues. Translation and notes: Tufan Gunduz. Yedditepe Publishing House-Istanbul. p.248
- Ershahin, S. (2002). Akkoyunlular. Political, cultural, economic and social history. Ankara. p. 317
- Okay, A. A study on miniature styles and problems that developed in Iran and its surroundings in the 15th century. Gazi University, Faculty of Science and Literature, Department of Art History. Ankara. pp. 347-364
- Bayramov, R. (2013). Typological classification of Azerbaijani architectural monuments of the 11th-18th centuries. East-West-Baku. p. 136
- Bağırılı, R. (2008). Analysis of tombstones with figures of horse and ram (sheep) of Akkoyunlu Karakoyunlu era from the point of view of contemporary ceramic art.T.C. Selcuk University. Konya. p.131
- Kırcaalı, A.K.Akkoyunlu state Diyarbakır Parlı (Iparlı) Safa Mosque Architectural features.T.C.Ondokuz Mayıs University-Faculty of Science and Literature art history.Samsun-2017.p.28
- Yusuf. K.H. Diyarbekir Jamileri 1. First Edition-August 2014. p. 140
- Hijran H.H., Hashim. Akdag. SWOT analysis method in the creation of strategic plans of Real Estate Cultural Assets; An example of Mardin Kasimiye (Sultan Kasim) Madrasah. *The Journal of International Lingual. Social and Educational Sciences* Year: 2018, Volume: 4, Number: 1, p.65-77
- History and Cultural Value of Nilgün F. Kasimiye Madrasah. *International Journal of Mardin Studies. (IJMS)*, 2024, 5(1), p. 68-79
- Harput during the period of Zekiye. T. Akkoyunlular. Firat University Harput Application and Research Center. Past to Future Harput Symposium. Elazig-23-25 May. p. 569-578
- Walter H. Uzun Hasan and Sheikh Junayd. (trans. Tevfik. B). Ankara 1992. p. 54
- Hamza. G. Akkoyunlu period architecture. *Türkler*. C-8. Ankara-226-273
- Ersay A.Y. Kosh-koyun head tombstones in Tabriz Azerbaijan museum. *International Journal of Social and Humanities Sciences research*. Ankara

University Faculty of Theology, Turkish Islamic Arts
History Main branch. Ankara 2023. p. 842-856

22. Jihat A.K. History revived in Şanlıurfa.
Şanlıurfa Governorship-Shurkay-Shevre arrangements

and restoration works 1990-1995. P.106; Jihat A.K.
Şanlıurfa çaçmileri. Şanlıurfa first edition 1993.

23. Aksoy M. History of stamps used on rugs and
ram and sheep head tombstones in Diyarbakır. Turkic
world studies TDA. vol. 122 issue 240. p. 99-106